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Determining the Causes of Cramming of Grade 9 STEP Students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School

In Partial Fulfillment of
the Requirements
for the subject
Practical Research I
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Science, Technology,
Engineering, and Mathematics
(STEM) Curriculum

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APPROVAL SHEET

This research with a title “***CAUSES OF CRAMMING TO GRADE 9 STUDENTS UNDER THE SCIENCE CURRICULUM OF RAMON MAGSAYSAY (CUBAO) HIGH SCHOOL***” is prepared by a Group from Grade 11 Senior High School students as part of fulfillment a project for the subject Practical Research I.

This research is accepted as compliance for the requirements for the subject Practical Research I.

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Marc Andrie M. Bermundo

Mary Shanelle L. Ejanda

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The Researchers

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CHAPTER 1: THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

It is hard to disaffirm the fact that the learnings that we took at school takes us to further heights. Schools may see our interests yield from a broad one to a specific course, be it from their skills at communication or mathematics, throughout the whole exhilarating journey of attaining education, these specific field of interest will naturally show. The path can be enthusiastic and gloomy at the same time, but the aspects of schooling is the same to every person, although it may differ vastly as time progresses.

Learning science is significant to the development of a country's advancement in the field of scientific learning – hence the creation of special science classes for intellectually-capable students. This is the reason on why the Science Education Institute (SEI) of the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) piloted the Engineering and Science Education Program (ESEP) or now called as the Science, Technology and Engineering Program (STEP) on 1994 and is now implemented to 198 different schools nationwide on 2013, according to an article posted by the Official Gazette of the Philippines on the same year.

Special classes are by definition, build-ups of intellectually capable students in a school setting, pitting them against top-notch quality education that is similar to the layout of the regular school system but with further elective subjects and in-depth topics that is learned by them in an earlier setting. Moreover, special classes are equal to the

environment of true science high schools in the country, which is tended upon by the local government of the school's vicinity along with SEI.

The modern face of learning in the Philippines began to release another protuberance in the stigma, and unfortunately became a rising tide amongst the learners. One of these predicaments is the inevitable cramming on school-based requirements and activities. Accompanied by this is the potential of students having mental health issues that can affect their overall well-being.

Since the procedures and fruits of learning are the characteristics of improvement that connotes amendment particularly for attitude and knowledge, it must be always and enjoyable experience to the eyes of the learners. The modifications of an education system must not reach a threatening level of distress to the students, but improve the quality of their capabilities in order for them to become the responsible pioneers of the future.

In the present study, the researchers would assess the causes of cramming to the Grade 9 Science, Technology, and Engineering Program (STEP) students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School (RMCHS) that comprises the three sections, namely 9-Newton, 9-Darwin, and 9-Einstein. The selected research locale is one of the schools in Quezon City to have a special Science class to support the development of intellectually-capable students. The school is one of the schools that are recognized by the DOST to be on par with Science High Schools in the Philippines.

The key objective of the present study will lead out to a developmental test seeking to help out Filipino Junior High School students in procrastination due to having the impasse of distress in their requirements and responsibilities in their respective academic institution. If successful, the results may be used to provide assistance in maintaining the welfare of Filipino students in lieu with their learning, entertainment, and relaxation that will guarantee a sound mind alongside with a healthy lifestyle for them.

Statement of the Problem

In this study, the researchers intend to seek the causes of cramming to students. This study will be done to the selected respondents hailing from the Grade 9 Science Curriculum students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School that comprises the three sections, namely 9-Newton, 9-Darwin, and 9-Einstein. This Research aims to find answers to the following questions:

1. What are the reasons of students to cram frequently during school days?
2. How does cramming affect the students in the following areas?
 - a. School Activities
 - b. Extracurricular Duties/School Clubs
 - c. Home Duties
 - d. Family Relationships
 - e. Peer Relationships
3. What are the scenarios of cramming in an urban public high school with students in the Special Science classes?
4. How would be this quandary can be solved, given by the possible differences of the students in learning styles and attitudes?
5. How does cramming affect the effectivity of learning in students?

Significance of the Study

The proponents aim to discover the various reasons that cause cramming to students through this, it may lead to finding solutions to the problem which can be beneficial. The benefits of the present study would contribute to the following:

- To the Students - The findings of this study will benefit the students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School since it focuses on the causes of cramming that is helpful for them in lessening the said habit.
- To the Teachers - The results of the study will assist them in creating new ways to approach their students that are facing the problems of cramming. Furthermore, teachers would be able to adjust to the capabilities of their students to fit the compulsory techniques that are still efficient to the learners while being effective in their approach.
- To the School Department Heads & Administration Staff - The findings of the study will benefit the leading head teachers and the staff because they can now study more about this underrated issue to provide a solution in their own way so they can dissipate new practices while being methodical to the mandate of teaching.
- To the Researchers - The conclusions of the study will be beneficial to the researchers in their process in being research-oriented and well-being. It can help them improve their learning process by determining the goal of the given study, which is all about the possible and observable causes of cramming.
- To the Future Researchers - They may find this study useful if they will take this as an inspiration or reference for their own study.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The present study tackles about the causes of cramming in students in a Science Curriculum setting. This study does not comprise any other bonafide Junior High School or Senior High School student as respondents of the said school for the Academic Year 2019 – 2020.

The answers given by the respondents in the study are from the survey given by the researchers. The researchers are also unbiased in giving out personal inferences in the results of the study in a way that it would fit into the present study.

This research study only focuses on finding reasons behind cramming that may lead to further discovery of solution.

Specifically, the study will only look upon the causes of cramming on the selected 9th graders of the Newton, Darwin, and Einstein, all of which are in the Science, Technology, and Engineering Program (STEP) students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School.

CHAPTER 2: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Review of Related Literature

This chapter includes the ideas, finished thesis, dissertations, generalization or conclusions, methodologies, and others. Those that were encompassed within this chapter helps in familiarizing important information that are relevant and similar to the present study.

Related Literature

According to Calub (2018), the implementation of Republic Act 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 changed the layout of the school system, which is now a challenge for school administrators and education heads alike to line up the best pedagogical treatment for their students.

In a paper done by Reynolds (2015) in detailing the factors of procrastination amongst undergraduate college students, it is stated that there may be other factors that may denote to procrastination and cramming as a whole. In his findings, it is noted that the samples may have produced a significant number of details in the actual finding of the root causes of procrastination and/or cramming such as a person's locus of control, his/her personality and external factors such as the environment he/she goes too. In the present study, some factors that are mentioned in his paper may be essential in getting a hold of the possible causes of procrastination and/or cramming to the selected respondents of this study.

A much more simplified conclusion can be found in the paper of Ojo (2019) in which he declares that some of the causes of procrastination in students include forgetfulness, the lack of clarity between teacher and student, overly-lenient deadlines, the fear of failure, external distractions, other obligations, and as a form of rebellion to their hated teachers. Obviously, some of it may apply to the respondents of the present study, but there might be other unknown factors that may be overshadowed in the Ojo's set-up.

Related Studies

Students that are affected with the change of the education system along with some external factors that may be distracting them from studying well. This is pinpointed by studies done by Cunanan and Mercado (2019) and Ilowa *et.al.* (2019) which studied about the impacts of stress and procrastination on the students of their respective schools. Concluding out from the papers, it is noteworthy that there are different distractions that hinder students from doing school requirements – a thing that is noticeable even in the respondents of the present study.

Another point can be seen right through a work done by Arzadon (2017), where she noted that amidst the promotion of diligence and effort to gain proper grades, many tend to be “killing” for the grade, where students tend to become superior against others for their own sake. In today's time, two things are common to two types of students. The

first one being lethargic, which is usually found in the lower sections, and slacking is a regular choice to do. The other one, is being too “competitive” against each other, which makes the students loss their passion in the true essence of learning things and is just collecting information in all subject matters just for the credit. This is an important side note in the present study as it can also reveal a peculiar case for student cramming – which is the competition that is happening amongst their classmates.

Statement of the Hypothesis

The possible reasons for the cramming of Grade 9 students under the Science Curriculum of the selected research setting can be determined, which indicates that solutions can be brought up along with the help of this study to minimize the aftermaths of these situations where students will cram on specific school requirements or obligations.

Research Paradigm

Figure 1.1: The relationship between the cramming of Grade 9 Science, Technology, and Engineering Program students and the findings of the probable causes of the said problems in Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School, Academic Year 2019-2020.

Definition of Terms:

1. **Case Study** – A qualitative research analyzing individual/s affected by factors relating to their environment.
2. **Cramming** – doing school works and assignments on a short period of time right before the deadline.
3. **Curriculum** – The lesson guides or modules that are taught to academic institutions.
4. **Education** – A form of gaining knowledge under a curriculum guide taught by teachers.
5. **STE** – Science, Technology and Engineering.
6. **Laziness** –The lack of will to do a certain activity.
7. **Procrastination** – The prolonging of doing school works due to various reasons.
8. **Qualitative Research** – A study about social sciences and psychological aspects.
9. **Simple Random Sampling** – A form of choosing respondents by selecting a group from a larger group with each member of the population having equal chances of being samples.
10. **STEP** - Science, Technology, and Engineering Program.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter will present a description of the research design selection and description of respondents, research instruments, data collection procedure, and statistical treatments used during the course of the study.

Research Design

The research study will do case study research under qualitative approach, with the purpose of establishing a foundation in finding out the causes of cramming to the academic performance of Grade 9 students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School under Science, Technology and Engineering Program and help to find possible solutions to overcome this problem after collecting specific data. The proponents will be executing the quota sampling technique to select respondents that possess characteristics for the target population.

The design's approach of the given study is qualitative since it involves the researcher's views and perceptions. According to Farooq in 2015, research design as an extensive cross-sectional approach, where a number of cases are considered at a particular time and the data is gathered to study the opinions, behavior, attitudes, habits, desires, values and beliefs etc. The gathered data will be analyzed and then explained to come up with a conclusion.

Determining the Sample Size

The respondents of the research study will come from Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School. The research will use quota sampling for the study for which the researchers will select Grade 9 Students under Science, Technology, and Engineering Program (STEP) that shows characteristics of cramming, but the samples will be limited using Slovin's formula.

After determining the population of the students in the sections they belong, we will use the Slovin's formula in order to substitute the data we collected which will give us to an approximate number of 28 respondents (see below) from the top three sections from the Science, Technology, and Engineering Program (STEP) of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School.

$$n = \frac{93}{1+93(0.025)} = 27.96992481; \approx 28$$

Research Instrument

In the present study, the researchers will use survey-questionnaire to gather data that is needed in conducting this study where the researchers select a sample of respondents from a population and administers a standardized questionnaire to them. The researchers will head out to the New Sonny Belmonte (NSB) Building to ask the Grade 9 Science, Technology, and Engineering Program (STEP) students to discover the causes of cramming to them. There will be five questions included in the survey questionnaire. Four of them will have particular answers for the given questions and one of them will provide opinion statement of the respondents. The researchers will go to different classrooms of the selected respondents and ask permission to the teacher on the scene, if ever there are classes ongoing, to permit them to conduct a survey. The survey would only take time in less than ten minutes.

The questions that are included in the survey-questionnaire are as follows:

1. How often do you cram requirements close to deadline?
 - a. Never

- b. Sometimes
 - c. Often
2. When there's a requirement to be passed on two weeks, you usually...
- a. Do it as soon as it was announced
 - b. Do it after stalling for a week
 - c. Do it 1-3 days before the deadline
3. On an average school day, how many hours do you spend on doing school works?
- a. More than 6 hours
 - b. 3-6 hours
 - c. Less than 3 hours
4. Rather than doing school works, what do you spend your time on?
- a. Going out
 - b. Playing games
 - c. Surfing the internet
 - d. Other: _____
5. What is the reason you cram? (shade all reasons applied to you)
- Laziness
 - Don't like the teacher of that subject
 - Not a major priority
 - Mind preoccupied with other stuff
 - Don't feel like it
 - Like to feel the rush of cramming
 - Other: _____

Data Gathering Procedure and Analysis

The data analysis that will be used for the present study is descriptive, in the form of quota sampling with the sample size being determined by the Slovin's formula.

The chosen population for the present study are the Grade 9 students of the sections of the Science, Technology, and Engineering Program (STEP) at Ramon

Magsaysay (Cubao) High School, which are the sections of 9-Newton, 9-Darwin, and 9-Einstein. The proponents will be executing the sampling technique to the selected respondents in order to cut down time and resource limitations. For this study, the researchers would use the Slovin's formula for obtaining the sample size. This is for the reason that (1) the population of the selected respondents is small and (2) for the ease of sampling the respondents.

Noting n as the sample size, we will arrive at the formula, which is:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

where the size of the population is denoted as N and e being stands for the margin of error (Almeda *et. al.*, 2010).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CONCLUSION

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REFERENCES

Almeda, J., Capistrano, T. and Sarte, G. (2010). *Elementary Statistics*. Quezon City: UP Press. Retrieved January 29, 2020 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235972107_Elementary_Statistics

Arzadon, M.M. (2017, December). Killing For The Grade. Retrieved January 29, 2020 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335581473_Killing_for_the_Grade

Calub, Cecilia L. (2018). Overcoming the Challenges in the Implementation and Administration of the K-12 Curriculum: Towards a Culture of Excellence. Retrieved January 29, 2020 from https://www.academia.edu/13000330/Overcoming_the_Challenges_in_the_Implementation_of_the_K-12_Curriculum_Towards_a_Culture_of_Excellence

Cunanan, Jan Wayne and Mercado, Virgilio Jr. (2019, March). Stress: Effect on the Studies of Grade 10 Students of Mangaldan National High School S.Y. 2018-2019. Retrieved January 29, 2020 from https://www.academia.edu/40264806/Stress_Effect_on_Studies_of_Grade_10_Students_of_Mangaldan_National_High_School_S.Y._2018-2019

Cochran, W. (1977). *Sampling Techniques*. 3rd Ed. New York: John Wiley and Sons, Inc. ISBN: 978-0-471-16240-7. Retrieved January 29, 2020 from https://www.academia.edu/29684662/Cochran_1977_Sampling_Techniques_Third_Edition

Easton, V. J. and McColl, J. H. (1997). Simple Random Sampling. Statistics Glossary v1.1. Retrieved January 25, 2020 from <http://www.stats.gla.ac.uk/steps/glossary/sampling.html#srs>

Farooq, U. (2015). Survey Research Definition, Steps & Research Design. *Study Lecture Notes*. Retrieved January 25, 2020, from <http://www.studylecturenotes.com/social-research-methodology/survey-research-definition-steps-research-design>.

Illowa *et.al.* (2019). Science behind Procrastination among Senior High School of Grade 11 Students Subject Excellence Awardee in Our Lady of Fatima University – Quezon City Campus. Retrieved January 29, 2020 from https://www.academia.edu/38624577/Science_Behind_Procrastination_from_Grade_11_Students_of_Our_Lady_of_Fatima_University

Mersdorf, S. (2016). Qualitative vs. Quantitative Research Methods. *CVENT Blog*. Retrieved January 25, 2020, from <https://blog.cvent.com/events/feedback-surveys/qualitative-vs-quantitative-research-methods/>

Ojo, A.A. (2019). The Impact of Procrastination on Students Academic Performance in Secondary Schools. *International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology Research (IJSAR)*. Retrieved January 29, 2020 from <http://www.eajournals.org/wp-content/uploads/The-Impact-of-Procrastination-on-Students-Academic-Performance-in-Secondary-Schools.pdf>

Punzalan, J.R. & Tejada, J. (1992). On the Misuse of Slovin's Formula. *The Philippine Statistician*. Vol. 61, No. 1, pp. 129-136. Retrieved January 25, 2020 from http://www.psai.ph/tps_details.php?p=1&id=26

Reynolds, J.P. (2015). Factors Affecting Academic Procrastination. *Masters Theses & Specialist Projects*. Paper 1511. Retrieved January 25, 2020 from <https://digitalcommons.wku.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2516&context=theses>

APPENDICES

Appendix I – Derivation of the Sampling Technique

The usage of the Slovin's formula is heavily inclined by researchers and statisticians because of its convenience, but it is heavily misused as noted by Punzalan & Tejada in 2012. In order to derive the formula, we will look back to the work of Cochran in 1977 in which he presented the following formula below when working for a finite population, which is used for creating inferences on the population proportion P under simple random sampling without replacement (abbreviated as SRSWOR).

The formula given by Cochran in 1977 is

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{n_0}{N}}$$

where:

$$n_0 = \frac{z^2 p(1 - p)}{e^2}$$

N is the population size, z is the standard normal variate based on the confidence coefficient, p is the estimate for P , and e is a specified margin of error. Assuming a 95% of confidence so z is approximately equal to 2, we will end up through the Slovin's formula. In cases where P is absent to the knowledge of the researchers, the conservational approach is to maximize.

$$p(1 - p) = \frac{1}{4} - \left(\frac{1}{2} - p\right)^2$$

Noting that this quantity is maximized when the subtrahend is 0, that is, when $p = 0.5$. We then introduce $p = 0.5$ and $z = 2$ in the equation for n_0 does yield into

$$n_0 = \frac{2^2(0.5)(1 - 0.5)}{e^2} = \frac{1}{e^2}$$

in order for the formula to become

$$n = \frac{\frac{1}{e^2}}{1 + \frac{e^2}{N}} = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

which is now the Slovin's formula. This implies that both Cochran's formula and Slovin's fomula do coincide when estimating P using a confidence coefficient of 95% and 0.5 for the estimation of the population proportion (Punzalan & Tejada, 2012).

Appendix II – Survey Questions

The following are the survey questions that are used by the researchers in the present study. The researchers would head out to the New Sonny Belmonte (NSB) Building to ask the Grade 9 Science, Technology, and Engineering Program (STEP) students to discover the causes of cramming to them. There will be five questions included in the survey questionnaire. Four of them are close ended which means that there will be particular answers for the given questions and one of them is open ended, to obtain the statement opinion of the respondents. The researchers will go to different classrooms of the selected respondents and ask permission to the teacher on the scene, if ever there are classes ongoing, to permit them to conduct a survey. The survey would only take time in less than ten minutes.

The questions that are included in the survey-questionnaire are as follows:

1. How often do you cram requirements close to deadline?
 - a. Never
 - b. Sometimes
 - c. Often

2. When there's a requirement to be passed on two weeks, you usually...
 - a. Do it as soon as it was announced
 - b. Do it after stalling for a week
 - c. Do it 1-3 days before the deadline

3. On an average school day, how many hours do you spend on doing school works?
 - a. More than 6 hours
 - b. 3-6 hours
 - c. Less than 3 hours

4. Rather than doing school works, what do you spend your time on?

- a. Going out
- b. Playing games
- c. Surfing the internet
- d. Other: _____

5. What is the reason you cram? (shade all reasons applied to you)

- Laziness
- Don't like the teacher of that subject
- Not a major priority
- Mind preoccupied with other stuff
- Don't feel like it
- Like to feel the rush of cramming
- Other: _____

Appendix III – Informed Consent Letter

The researchers will utilize this informed consent letter when doing the data collection procedure of the present study. Below is the plain text view of the said letter.

INFORMED CONSENT LETTER

Greetings!

In compliance with the subject of Practical Research 1, the student researchers of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School - Senior High School (RMCHS – SHS) would like to inform you that they will be conducting a qualitative research study upon your advisory in the academic year 2019-2020.

The study entitled, “**Causes Of Cramming To Grade 9 Students Under The Science Curriculum Of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School**” aims to find out the reasons of students causing them to cram on said activities and why cramming affects them badly. They have chosen this topic because they have noted out that many students tend to cram over school requirements and there are some situations on which some of them cannot pass on time. In the present study, they have chosen the Grade 9 Science, Technology, and Engineering Program (STEP) students as their chosen respondents.

With this regard, we would humbly like to request from you to allow the student researchers to conduct their study upon their chosen respondents.

Thank you and God bless!